

Artificial Intelligence: Fuel for Growth in Japan Economy

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Abstract

The objective of this paper is to understand the changing trends in population composition in Japan and to understand the advantages of Artificial Intelligence. After examining the literature of Japan's Total fertility rate and Demographic change it clearly reveals future crisis that Japan Economy may face. Apart from the efforts of Japan Government policies to address population crisis, but it appears a very little impact to mitigate the decline in Total Fertility Rate. So there is a serious threat in terms of work force and it looks that greater attention should be given to artificial intelligence to bridge the gap between the total population and working population.

Keywords: Japan Population Crisis, Working Population, Government policy, Total Fertility Rate, Artificial Intelligence.

Introduction

"A finite world can support only a finite population; therefore, population growth must eventually equal zero"

- Garrett Hardin

Demography is the statistical description and analysis of population composition. It indicates the numbers of people distributed based on age and sex, birth and rates among various parameters of populations. Study of population helps us to understand the causes and consequences of changing population composition. The changes in population composition mainly depends on the changing rate of birth, deaths and migration.

Population Status in Japan

Japan collects census information every five years. The Statistics Bureau of the Ministry of Internal Affairs and Communication undertakes the process of conducting population survey in Japan. According to recent survey, Japan is witnessing a shrinking population at a record pace of 244,000 people in 2013 as birth declines and deaths rate increased. It is estimated, that nearly third of its total population may decrease in next 50 years, raising fears about its scarcity of labor supply and future Economic prospects.

According to the United Nations, nearly 48% of the world’s population lives in a country where birth rates are not sufficient to sustain existing populations, that means Japan may the problems of aging population (40% of Japanese will be over 65 by the year 2060) and not enough babies (there were 6,000 fewer births in 2013 than the previous years). Since 2010, Japan has experienced net population loss due to falling birth rates and almost no immigration, despite having one of the highest life expectancies in the world at 81.25 years of age as on 2006. The Population peaked in 2008 at 128,083,960 and had fallen 285,256 by October 2011 and most of them located in urban areas.

Objectives of the study

- To study the aging factor in population
- To examine the role of Artificial Intelligence

Aging factor in population

• Population Growth rate

According to 2015 censuses of National Institute of Population and Social Security Research, Japan population will decrease by one million every year by 2025, which result in declining trends of population by 86 million by 2060. More than 60% of the Population is expected to be over age of 65 years. According UN and PRB estimate, the Population ranking of Japan decreased from 7th to 11th in the initial stage of 21st century.

Year	Percentage Growth of Population
1985	3.40%
1990	2.10%
1995	1.60%
2000	1.10%
2005	0.70%
2010	0.20%
2015	-0.7%

Source: NIPSSR 2015

The Population of Japan in terms of percentage growth has declined from 3.40% in 1985 to negative growth rate i.e., -0.7% in 2015. It is a decreasing at a very rapid pace which amounts to a Demographic Disaster.

Aging of Japan Population

The population of Japan is aging faster compared to other countries. The population above 65 years have doubled in 24 years, i.e., from 7.1% to 14.1% between 1971-1994. According to Health and Welfare Ministry of Japan estimates 40% of Japan population will be above 65 years by 2060. This trend has triggered Japan Economy in terms of future national economic growth and its welfare.

Changing Age Composition of Japan Population from 1935-2015

Year	Total Population	Population by age		
		0-14	15-64	Above 64
1995	125,570	15.9	69.4	14.5
2000	126,962	14.6	67.9	17.3
2005	127,768	13.7	65.8	20.1
2010	128,058	13.2	63.7	23.1
2015	127,095	12.6	60.7	26.6
2017	126,714	12.3	59.9	27.8

Sources: Census of Japan

Japan faces massive demographic problems that will not go away. It is dangerous and selfish to leave it to future generations to find solutions. Like climate change, it behooves the leaders of this generation to face up to the challenges and start tackling the issues with vision and determination.

The Age composition of Japan Population is huge threat and a real challenge. The Population growth more than 65 years which was 7.1% in 1970 increased to 27.8% in 2017.

The Role of Artificial Intelligence

The future mantra of Economic Growth in Japan Economy should be on the grounds of Demographic changes. Investment on Artificial Intelligence, Internet of things and Robotic technology becomes pre-requisite for achieving better economic growth. Japan's Graying population is demographic disaster and Japan has to rethink its strategy of economic progress to balance the required workforce and existing trends in workforce. Expert team report has warned that the country is facing demographic disaster in terms of working and aging population and hence future, Japan economy may face severe shortage of young working population. The Government initiatives in this regard should be on strengthening the supply side of economy in order to achieve sustainable development.

The Investment in Artificial Intelligence becomes inevitable for sustaining future economic growth. Even though, Japan is the leader of industrial robotic technology but its implementation in their industries is only 20% compared to 40% in USA. It should also focus on the training more tech-savvy labour to balance the shrinking population.

Role of Education

Education in Japan plays an important role. The focus should be more on tech training sessions at the university level to keep their skill up to date. The Higher Education in Japan is also using Artificial Intelligence to train the students for futuristic growth. The Government of Japan is rewriting the blueprint for future growth strategy based on the use of Artificial Intelligence. Nomura Research Institute predicts that 50% of all jobs in Japan could be performed by Artificial

Intelligence enabled technology by 2035, so choosing the right mode is a crucial issue in terms of products and solutions is the need of Japanese Economy.

SWOT Analysis

Strengths

- Japan has a large pool of AI researchers
- Supportive Governmental policies
- Strong R&D Investment

Weaknesses

- Slow implementation of innovations
- Less use of AI in Japanese industries compared to USA and China
- High competition on the global scale

Opportunities

- Aging Working Population
- Improvement in value chain of industry

Threats

- Japan's AI industry is slow in introducing open-source AI platforms

Conclusion

Artificial Intelligence is the future mantra of economic development. One of the main takeaways for other economy which are enjoying the demographic dividend should also think the future prospect in terms of demographic changes. Artificial intelligence will be a new factor of production with the potential to introduce new sources of growth and reinforcing the role of people to drive growth in business.